

A SERIALIZATION FORMATS AND CLARITY

We support three encodings that trade off naturalness, precision, and token cost. We now detail each format, provide a small running example, and record strengths and weaknesses observed during development.

A.1 Natural language

Example description.

“The rooms are numbered 0, 3, 6, 5, and 8. Room 0 is connected to all other rooms. Room 5 shares a hallway with room 6. Room 3 is linked to room 8. And room 8 is also connected with room 6. You can only travel to adjacent, directly connected rooms at each turn.”

Observed failure mode. Agents frequently misinterpreted connections and later annotated in the belief state that rooms 8 and 3 are not connected even though the map includes edge 8–3. The likely causes include:

- Many different verbs for edges: “is connected”, “shares a hallway”, “is linked”, “is also connected”. Repeating a single term for edges improves directness and reduces ambiguity.
- The sentence “Room 0 is connected to all other rooms” encodes four implicit edges at once (0–5, 0–6, 0–8, 0–3). Making all edges explicit improves recall.
- Lack of helpful redundancy. A clearer alternative reads: “Room 3 is connected to rooms 0 and 8. Room 8 is connected to rooms 0, 3, and 6.”

Takeaway. Careful prompt editing may reduce errors, yet natural language contains many nuanced choices that create opportunities for misreading under time pressure. Our application needs clarity above all, so we favor more structured encodings when scale and reliability matter most.

A.2 Adjacency list

Format.

```
----- MAP (adjacency list) -----  
Each line shows: Room : directly connected rooms  
0 : 3 5 6 8  
3 : 0 8  
5 : 0 6  
6 : 0 5 8  
8 : 0 3 6
```

Pros. The format is direct and leaves no room for ambiguity or missed edges. During early tests, the agent parsed the default 5-node map flawlessly and navigated optimally.

Limits at scale. As maps grow, the list expands and readability degrades. For Default and Medium, the agent continued to plan well. For Hard, we started to observe occasional re-exploration as the agent looked for undiscovered bombs even after visiting relevant rooms. The effect remained mild because the agent still followed near-optimal paths most of the time. For Village, the list became long enough to overwhelm the model. We observed circular exploration, back-and-forth movement between a pair of rooms, and delayed assistance when a teammate called for help. The high token mass from the map combined with task rules and coordination messages created an unreadable prompt. Appendix C illustrates the adjacency lists for Default, Medium, Hard and Village maps.

B PROMPTS FOR REPRODUCIBILITY

We include the exact text used during the interaction loop so others can replicate our prompts. We preserve line breaks and spacing. We only normalize explicit “\n” markers into actual newlines and render any Unicode escape codes as plain characters. We are committed to *open science* and code release upon publication.

B.1 Initialization: game rules and setup (system + user content)

You are playing a text game with the user. Welcome to our interactive text game!
You are a specialist on a three-person search-and-rescue team. Your call sign is alpha.

----- ROLE AND OBJECTIVE -----

- * Defuse all 5 hidden bombs as fast as possible.
- * A team earns 10 x (number of phases) points for each bomb defused.
- * Maximize the final team score.

----- ENVIRONMENT MAP -----

The facility is a connected graph of rooms labeled with integers:
The map is partitioned into letter-labelled regions. Your starting region was region C.

- * **What you can see:** every room inside your current region and each neighboring region, shown as a single entry labelled by its letter.
- * **How to move:** to enter an adjacent region, treat it like a room and select the action **Move to Room <letter>**. Once inside, newer region's internal rooms will be revealed and the ones from the origin region hidden.
- * **Team communication:** always name both room numbers and region letters when asking for help or coordinating. Teammates in other regions cannot see the rooms visible to you.

Your starting region view, where each line is 'Room : directly connected to Rooms'

```
23 : 45 B A
45 : 48 65 55 23
48 : 66 68 69 45 49 A
49 : 48 56 A
55 : 45
56 : 49
65 : 45 71
66 : 48
68 : 48 75 77
69 : 48
71 : 65
75 : 68
77 : 68
A : 23 48 49
B : 23
```

You may move only to rooms listed as directly connected to your current location.

----- BOMB TYPES -----

- * Bombs may have 1, 2, or 3 color phases. Defuse them by applying the matching colored tools in order.

----- TOOLS PER PLAYER -----

- * Alpha - red, green
- * Bravo - green, blue
- * Charlie - blue, red

----- VALID ACTIONS -----

1. Move to an adjacent room/region -> Move to Room X
2. Inspect a bomb's phase list -> Inspect Bomb
3. Apply a wire cutter tool -> Apply <Color> Tool

----- COMMUNICATION -----

- * Each round you may append ONE message to teammates (they will read it next round).

----- OBSERVATION INFO -----

At the start of every round you learn:

- * Current round number and cumulative team score
- * Your room contents (bombs, players)
- * Locations of teammates
- * Messages sent in the previous round

----- REPLY FORMAT -----

To facilitate our interaction, reply your action selection and communication messages in this fixed format: Action selection: Your action. Message to Team: "Your Message". To move to an adjacent room, say: 'Move to Room X'. To inspect the sequence of a bomb in your current room, say: 'Inspect Bomb'. To apply a wire cutter tool, say: 'Apply X Tool'. Remember, your replies must adhere strictly to these rules.

Are you ready to begin?

B.2 Round 1: alpha initial belief state and first action prompt

----- BELIEF STATE -----

Role: Player alpha
Current round: 1 | Team score: 0

----- POSITION -----

You are in Room 68
Other players here: alpha, bravo, charlie

----- ROOM CONTENTS -----

Bomb 4: sequence UNKNOWN
No other bombs detected in this room.
Contents of all rooms:
Unexplored Rooms: 0, 3, 5, 6, 8, 11, 12, 14, 15, 16, 17, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 26, 27, 28, 31, 32, 33, 34, 36, 38, 40, 41, 43, 45, 46, 47, 48, 49, 51, 52, 53, 55, 56, 57, 58, 63, 64, 65, 66, 67, 68, 69, 70, 71, 72, 73, 75, 77 (remove as exploration progresses)
Explored rooms: ... (add as exploration progresses)

----- TEAMMATE LOCATIONS -----

alpha - Room 68
bravo - Room 68
charlie - Room 68

----- MAP (adjacency list) -----

The map is partitioned into letter-labelled regions. Your starting region was region C.

- * **What you can see:** every room inside your current region and each neighboring region, shown as a single entry labelled by its letter.
- * **How to move:** to enter an adjacent region, treat it like a room and select the action **Move to Room <letter>**. Once inside, newer region's internal rooms will be revealed and the ones from the origin region hidden.
- * **Team communication:** always name both room numbers and region letters when asking for help or coordinating. Teammates in other regions cannot see the rooms visible to you.

Each line shows 'Room : directly connected rooms'

```
23 : 45 B A
45 : 48 65 55 23
48 : 66 68 69 45 49 A
49 : 48 56 A
55 : 45
56 : 49
65 : 45 71
66 : 48
68 : 48 75 77
69 : 48
71 : 65
75 : 68
77 : 68
A : 23 48 49
B : 23
```

----- KNOWN BOMBS -----

Bomb 4 | Room 68 | Phase list: UNKNOWN | Status: UNKNOWN
(4 bombs remain unlocated, 0 bombs defused)

----- RECENT MESSAGES -----

alpha : None
bravo : None
charlie : None

----- TOOL INVENTORY -----

alpha - red, green
bravo - green, blue
charlie - red, blue

----- INFORMATION I SHOULD SHARE -----

----- ACTION SYNTAX -----

Move : Move to Room X
Inspect Bomb : Inspect Bomb
Apply tool : Apply <Color> Tool
Send message : Message to Team: "..."
There is no standby action, but you can inspect a bomb if there is any in the room.

Given the above belief state, alpha, what is your next action?

B.3 Round 1: agent replies

Each agent receives their own version of Prompt B.2 and replies accordingly.

Action selection: Inspect Bomb
Message to Team: "Alpha inspecting Bomb 4 in Room 68 (region C)"

Action selection: Move to Room 75
Message to Team: "Heading to Room 75 (Region C) to explore."

Action selection: Move to Room 48
Message to Team: "Alpha please Inspect Bomb in Room 68; Charlie moving to Room 48 to explore."

B.4 Round 2: alpha observation and instruction to update belief

Each agent receives their own version of this prompt with personal observations and each response updates the corresponding belief state.

Your observation is: Round: 2. Total team score: 0. Previous action results (inspect bomb): You inspected Bomb 4. This bomb is a 2-stage bomb and its remaining sequence is Blue-Green. Room contents: You are currently in Room 68. Contents of this room include alpha, Bomb 4. You are in region C. Your current map view is:

```
23 : 45 B A
45 : 48 65 55 23
48 : 66 68 69 45 49 A
49 : 48 56 A
55 : 45
56 : 49
65 : 45 71
66 : 48
68 : 48 75 77
69 : 48
71 : 65
75 : 68
77 : 68
A : 23 48 49
B : 23
```

Communication is available this round.

Communication messages sent by your teammates: Player alpha: "alpha inspecting bomb 4 in room 68 (region c)". Player bravo: "heading to room 75 (region c) to explore.". Player charlie: "alpha please inspect bomb in room 68; charlie moving to room 48 to explore.". Please update your belief state based on the above observation, and send me your results in the same format as previously. DO NOT add additional explanations. Return your answer beginning with: 'Below is your current belief'

B.5 Loop protocol

After alpha updates the belief state, the *next-action* prompt repeats with the new belief. If the agent changes region, the map view switches to the current region while exterior regions collapse to single-line entries. The loop continues until the team defuses all bombs or the time limit is reached.

B.6 Mid Game (High Coordination Round)

Action selection: Apply red tool
Message to Team: "bomb 4 red wire cut. remaining phase: blue. bravo, apply your blue tool now."

Action selection: Apply blue tool
Message to Team: "alpha will cut red first; i'm applying blue now to finish defusing bomb 4."

Action selection: Move to Room 38
Message to Team: "alpha, please cut the red on bomb 4 now; bravo, be ready with blue next round. i'm moving to room 38 to search for the last bomb."

B.7 Invalid action feedback messages

We now show example outputs for each invalid action type the environment can emit. We include a brief explanation before each sample and then the exact style of message the environment returns. Any action that fits one of these categories is labeled as invalid and lowers the *Valid Action Rate*. The agent loses the turn and gets the corresponding feedback message at the start of the next round.

1) *Null action.* Explanation: the agent did not provide an action object for this round.

Invalid action.

2) *Unrecognized action object.* Explanation: the action object is not Inspect Bomb, not a node move, and not a tool; it matches none of the handled cases.

Your action is invalid.

3) *Inspect with no bomb present.* Explanation: the agent tried to inspect, but the current room has no bomb bound to the agent (e.g., Room 48).

There is no bomb in the current location, Room 48, for you to inspect.

4) *Move to a non-adjacent room.* Explanation: the requested destination is not adjacent to the agent current room (e.g., tried Room 69 from Room 68).

You cannot directly move to Room 69 because it is not adjacent to your current location, Room 68. Consider taking a detour to another room first and then move to your destination.

5) *Apply a tool when there is no bomb in the room.* Explanation: the agent attempted to apply a bomb tool, but there is no bomb at the current location (e.g., Room 68 without an active bomb bound to the agent).

There is no bomb in your current location, room 68, for you to defuse.

6) *Apply the wrong color tool (sequence mismatch). Explanation: the agent holds a valid bomb tool but its color does not match the bomb next required color (e.g., applied GREEN when the remaining sequence begins with BLUE-GREEN).*

You cannot apply Tool green to Bomb 4 because the sequence of this bomb is [Blue, Green]. You will need to apply other color tool first.

7) *Apply a tool the agent does not have / non-bomb tool. Explanation: the selected tool is not in the agent inventory as a usable bomb-defusal tool (e.g., alpha tried to use blue).*

You do not have blue. Consider asking your teammates who have this tool to help you defuse the bomb.

C MAP VARIATIONS

We evaluate four maps that scale in size and complexity. Default, Medium, and Hard are strict subgraphs of the Village map, a segmented model map that simulates a real village layout. Figure 6 presents drawings for all four maps with integer labeled nodes.

C.1 Graph statistics

Table 2 reports exact counts and basic structural metrics computed from the adjacency lists below. We calculate average degree as $2|E|/|V|$ and diameter as the maximum shortest path distance.

Table 2: Structural statistics for each map.

Map	$ V $	$ E $	Avg. degree	Diameter
Default	5	7	2.80	2
Medium	8	10	2.50	3
Hard	16	24	3.00	6
Village	53	71	2.68	10

C.2 Adjacency lists

Figures 2, 3, and 4 include the exact adjacency lists used to compute Table 2, while Figure 6 shows their drawings. Default, Medium, and Hard appear as subgraphs inside the Village map.

```

----- MAP (Default) -----
0 : 3 5 6 8
3 : 0 8
5 : 0 6
6 : 0 5 8
8 : 0 3 6

```

Figure 2: Default map as adjacency list.

```

----- MAP (Medium) -----
23 : 47 73
34 : 38 41 57
38 : 34 53
41 : 34 47
47 : 23 41 57 73
53 : 38 73
57 : 34 47
73 : 23 47 53

```

Figure 3: Medium map as adjacency list.

```

----- MAP (Hard) -----
0 : 3 5 6 8
3 : 0 8 14
5 : 0 6
6 : 0 5 8 20 23
8 : 0 3 6 14
14 : 3 8 31 34
20 : 6
23 : 6 47 73
31 : 14 34
34 : 14 31 38 41 57
38 : 34 53
41 : 34 47
47 : 23 41 57 73
53 : 38 73
57 : 34 47
73 : 23 47 53

```

Figure 4: Hard map as adjacency list.

```

----- MAP (Village) -----
0 : 3 5 6 8
3 : 0 8 14 15 17 21
5 : 0 6 12 16 22 27
6 : 0 5 8 11 20 23 24
8 : 0 3 6 14
11 : 6
12 : 5
14 : 3 8 17 28 31 34
15 : 3
16 : 5
17 : 3 14 21 40
20 : 6 24 26 27
21 : 3 17
22 : 5
23 : 6 24 45 47 73
24 : 6 20 23 26 32 46
26 : 20 24 32 36
27 : 5 20
28 : 14 33
31 : 14 34 40 48 49
32 : 24 26 43
33 : 28
34 : 14 31 38 41 57
36 : 26
38 : 34 53
40 : 17 31 52
41 : 34 47
43 : 32 51
45 : 23 48 55 65
46 : 24 58 67 70 72
47 : 23 41 57 73
48 : 31 45 49 66 68 69
49 : 31 48 56
51 : 43 63 64
52 : 40
53 : 38 73
55 : 45
56 : 49
57 : 34 47
58 : 46
63 : 51
64 : 51
65 : 45 71
66 : 48
67 : 46
68 : 48 75 77
69 : 48
70 : 46
71 : 65
72 : 46
73 : 23 47 53
75 : 68
77 : 68

```

Figure 5: Village map as adjacency list.

